

Millennial Generation Decisions in Choosing Vocational Schools

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ABSTRACT

The choices of vocational high schools are numerous and diverse in Jakarta. Many alternative choices provide an easier decision making for candidate students according to their interests and economic abilities. This study aimed to analyze the influence of the variables of quality, trust, brand image on the decision to choose in SMKN 53 and SMK Telkom in Jakarta. The data were analyzed using path analysis. Hypothesis testing method was done using a structural equation model (SEM) analysis with SmartPLS statistical application. The result showed that the trust variable and quality variable were significant with brand image in SMKN 53 and SMK Telkom, while in SMK Telkom the trust variable was not significant with the brand image. The trust variable was significant towards the decision to choose in SMKN 53, while it was not significant in SMK Telkom. The quality variable was not significant towards the decision to choose in Public Vocational School, while it was significant in Private Vocational School. The quality variable was significant with the trust variable in two schools. The brand image variable was significant towards the decision to choose in SMKN 53, while it was not significant in SMK Telkom. The quality and trust variables were significant with the intervening brand image variable in SMKN 53, while they were not significant in SMK Telkom. The quality and choice variables were significant with the intervening brand image variable in SMKN 53, while they were not significant in SMK Telkom

Keywords: Brand Image, Decision to choose, Trust and Quality

INTRODUCTION

Millennial generation is a generation born in the 2000s (Howe & Strauss), where at the year there are many new technologies have emerged in the community. In the millennial era, this generation is easily facilitated in obtaining information and entertainment by the existence of technological tools such as smartphones that can be used to share many needs.

According to (Lyons, 2004) the millennial generation is a generation who

actively uses smartphones to send messages or to communicate to friends by using media such as e-mail, SMS, instant messaging and other social media such as Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram. The characteristics of the millennial generation are generations that are active in social media and whose lives are greatly affected by the presence of new technology.

According to (Meier, Austin, and Crocker, 2010), Millennial generations or generation Y were born in the era of

information technology development and the world of education so that they have different behaviors than the previous generation. Characteristics of the millennial generation will tend to be critical when they will do something.

The presence of the millennial generation has made schools innovate in marketing strategies to get students to attend Vocational Schools. Based on data obtained from the Ministry of Education and Culture in 2017, more students are interested in Vocational School than High School. It can be seen in Table 1

Table 1: Flow of High School and Vocational School Students

School	Learners	Graduates of Students
High School	4.659.542	1.263.211
Vocational School	4.682.913	1.285.176

Source: Ministry of Education and Culture 2017

State and Private Vocational Schools become the choice for students in the millennial era. Each of these two schools must have characteristics and excellence to be chosen by the current millennial generation. It can be seen in Table 2, list of students based on their interests of State Vocational Schools and Private Vocational Schools in Indonesia:

Table 2: Flow of State Vocational School Students

School	Learners
State Vocational School	2.004.055
Private Vocational School	2.678.858

Source: Ministry of Education and Culture 2017

Millennial can easily search for information of school which is going to be chosen by them by using a smartphone. School marketing strategy by using brochures and banners, in the millennial era, has rarely been seen by this generation. They are very active in social media, therefore Trust, Quality, and Brand Image factors greatly influence the millennial's decision in choosing SMK.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Doney and Cannon in Aydin and Ozer (2005) state that trust is a result obtained from the process of calculating costs that has been spent, whereas according

to Akbar and Parvez (2009) trust is a stable and collaborative relationship that is seen as one of the relevant antecedents, then according to Lau & Lee (1999) state positive behavior towards the second party and one party trusting the other party will lead to mutual trust. Ganesan and Shankar in Jasfar (2009) state that trust is a reference from: 1. Credibility is the result of job reliability and effectiveness that requires certain skills to create great trust in an organization. 2. Policy is a condition where commitment is not formed, when the amount of trust is based on goals and motivations that are the advantages of other organizations when new conditions arise. Trust is built because of the expectation that other parties will act according to the needs and desires of consumers (Ryan, 2002). Consumers, especially prospective students, directly choose when trust is built well by the two schools. School quality factors can influence the selection of student decision.

Quality is a comparison between expectation and performance to a statement of an attitude (Kotler, 2013). According to Sviokla in (Lupiyoda, 2013) product quality has several indicators, they are: 1. Performance, aspects of individual performance that can be measured which refers to the character of the core product that includes the brand. 2. Product diversity, each individual is measured subjectively 3. Service capability, the service capability of a product produces a conclusion of product quality. 4. Compliance with calculation errors including completion of time from a level of accuracy that can be measured, after a factor of trust and quality. Brand image is also a factor seen by students.

One intangible asset is equity represented by a brand (Main, 2007). Supporting factors to form a brand image in relation to brand associations are: 1. Favorability of brand association, 2. Strength of brand association, and 3. Uniqueness of brand association. Therefore, competitive advantage must be created that can be used as an excuse for consumers to choose a particular brand by positioning the

brand more towards experience or self-benefit from the product image (Keller, 2003).

Factors of Trust, Quality, and Brand Image must be owned by State Vocational Schools and Private Vocational Schools in the current millennial era. It is because of the millennial generation is very critical of things seen in fact not just promises given by the school through media brochures or banners presented at the time of acceptance of new students. The decision to choose is influenced by factors of Trust, Quality and Brand Image.

According to (Peter and Olson, 2000) purchasing decision is a connected process that combines knowledge to evaluate two or more alternative behaviors and choose one of them. According to Kotler and Armstrong (2008) that purchasing decision is the stage of process where consumers actually make a purchase.

The two schools that researchers studied both had advantages over other schools. Telkom Vocational School is a school under the guidance of the Indonesian telecommunications industry and State Vocational High School 53 which is a State Vocational High School which is fostered by a leading automotive motorbike industry

company in Indonesia. Based on the formulation of the problem, this study aims to identify the character of the students of Telkom Vocational High School and Vocational High School 53, knowing the effect of quality and trust on brand image in two schools, knowing the effect of brand image on the decision to choose.

MATERIALS & METHODS

This research was conducted at Telkom Vocational High School (SMK Telkom) and 53 State Vocational High School (SMKN 53) on May 2018 until June 2018. The selection of research locations was based on the achievements of each of the two schools.

The type of research is descriptive quantitative, which aims to describe and express a problem, situation, and event as it is or reveal facts in depth about trust, quality, and brand image of the decision of students in choosing SMK in DKI Jakarta.

The measurement scale used in this research is Likert scale. This scale allows respondents to express the intensity of respondents' feelings (Najir, 2005).

In this study the variables used include in the following Table 3 below:

Table 3 Research variable

Variable	Indikator	Information
Trust(X1) Kotler,2012	Wellness(X1.1)	Consumer Trust in seller behavior
	Ability (X1.2)	The ability to convince buyers and provide satisfaction and security
	Integrity (X1.3)	A person's belief in the seller's honesty
	Willingness to depend (X1.4)	Acceptance of possible risks or negative consequences
Quality (X2) Parasuraman, Zeithaml and Berry, 1985	Direct evidence (X2.1)	Includes physical facilities, equipment, employees and means of communication
	Reliability (X2.2)	The ability to provide accurate and satisfying services.
	Responsiveness (X2.3)	The desire to help consumers and provide the best service possible.
	Confidence (X2.4)	Knowledge and politeness of employees and the ability to foster trust in the company or school
	Empathy (X2.5)	Ease of conducting relationships, good communication, personal attention and understanding the needs of customers
Brand Image (X3) Keller, 2003	Excellence towards the Brand (X3.1)	Where a product is superior in competition
	Brand Strength (X3.2)	Information enters consumer memory and persists as part of brand image.
	The uniqueness of the brand (X3.3)	The uniqueness of the brand inevitably must be shared with other brands
Student Decision (Y) Alma, 2003	Product (Y)	Decisions chosen by students

Source: From various sources, 2018

The population of this study was students of class X at SMKN 53 Vocational School with 120 and Telkom State Vocational High Schools as many as 140. Researchers used SEM-PLS analysis by requiring at least 30 samples. The samples used were 65 samples from each school. Total sample of two schools are 130 samples. The decision took 65 samples from both schools. Researchers took half of the population of class X of each of the two schools.

The sampling technique used in this study is simple random sampling. Sampling of members of the population is conducted randomly by drawing through absent

numbers in each class, so that each student has the same opportunity to be selected as a sample in this study. Below is a picture of the SEM-PLS model from this study:

Figure 1. SEM-PLS Research Model

Based on Figure 1, the hypothesis in this study are as follows:

H1	There is an influence of trust on brand image in Telkom and SMKN 53
H2	There is an influence of trust in the decision to choose at Telkom and SMKN 53
H3	There is an influence of quality on trust choosing in Telkom and SMKN 53
H4	There is an influence of quality on brand image
H5	There is an influence of quality on the decision to choose
H6	There is an influence of brand image on the decision to choose
H7	There is an indirect effect of quality through trust in the brand image
H8	There is an indirect influence on quality through trust in the decision to choose
H9	There is an indirect influence on quality through brand image of the decision to choose

Statistical Analysis

The results of the study obtained profiles of respondents based on gender (gender), age, and majors of specialization taken by students, the profile of respondents can be seen in Table 4 below:

Table 4: Profile of Respondents of Vocational High School 53 and Telkom Vocational School based on Age

Vocational High School 53			Telkom Vocational School based on Age	
Age	total	percent	total	percent
14 year	-	-	1	1%
15 year	-	-	16	25%
16 year	44	68%	45	69%
17 year	21	32%	3	5%

Source: Processed by the author, 2018

Based on Table 4 comparison of ages between 53 State Vocational School and Telkom Vocational School that the characteristics of the age of the two schools are more dominant at the age of 16 with a presentation of 68% in SMKN 53 or as many as 44, while SMK Telkom is 69% or 45 people. Students in the age of 14-17 are able to determine which school they choose.

According to (Dahar, 1996) that at the age 11 years and above into the stage of formal operations where at this stage, the ability of students is already at the stage of abstract thinking. They are able to hypothesize, calculate the possible consequences, and test the hypotheses they make. According to (Bardick, Kerry, Magnusson & Kim, 2006) that at the age of 15-18 years, the stage of career development at that age begins to enter the phase of growth and exploration.

Table 5: Characteristics of Respondents in Vocational High School 53 and Telkom Vocational Schools by sex

Vocational High School 53			Telkom Vocational School based on Age	
sex	total	percent	total	percent
Male	65	100%	45	69%
Female	-	-	20	31%

Source: Processed by the author, 2018

Based on Table 5 the gender in the two schools is dominated by male, for SMKN 53 there are 65 people with a presentation of 100% of men. At SMK Telkom for male is 69% or as many as 45 people, while women

are 31% or as many as 20 people. This proves that the most students interested in Vocational Schools are male students. Based on research (Sri Lestari, 2016) regarding the rationality of students choosing vocational high schools, the results showed that most people choose vocational education because of interest in alumni who can directly enter the workforce, the desire

to work after graduating from school, whereas based on research (Winna Dharmayanti, 2014) the interest of students entering Vocational School in Pontianak is due to encouragement from family and the image produced by the Vocational School where each graduate is ready to enter the workforce.

Table 6: Respondents from Vocational High School 53 and Telkom Vocational Schools are based on the Department

Vocational High School 53			Telkom Vocational School based on Age	
Department	total	percent	total	percent
COMPUTER NETWORK ENGINEERING	65	100%	45	69%
SOFTWARE ENGINEERING	-	-	20	31%
TECHNICAL LIGHT VEHICLE	16	25%	-	-
WELLDING	16	24%	-	-
ELECTRICAL ENGINEERING	17	26%	-	-
TELECOMMUNICATION NETWORK	-	-	17	26%
TELECOMMUNICATION TRANSMISSION	-	-	16	24%

Source: Processed by the author, 2018

Based on Table 6 there are the same majors in these two schools, namely TKJ (Computer Networking Engineering) with the same presentation in two schools by 25% or as many as 16 people presentation of 26% or around 17 people. For the majors of TKR (Light Vehicle Engineering) in Vocational High School 53 and RPL (Software Engineering) at Telkom Vocational High Schools the same presentation value is 25% with a total of 16 people. The smallest presentation sample in the LAS majors in Vocational High School 53 and Transmission at Telkom Vocational Schools with 24% presentation or as many as 16 people. Students choose vocational schools based on the interest of the department provided by the school. According to (Crow & Crow, 2007) states that interest is a motive force that encourages someone to give attention to people, objects or activities or in other words the reason why someone gives attention and participates more towards objects or activities. According to (Hurlock, 1993) explaining that interest is a source of motivation that encourages someone to do what is done when freely choosing a decision.

Test Results for Construct Validity

The results of the construct validity test are done by looking at the value of Average Variance Extracted (AVE). Constructions are said to be valid / good if the AVE of each construct is > 0.50 (Noor, 2014). According to (Wijayanto, 2008) Minimum AVE value to state that reliability has been reached is 0.50. The results of validity can be seen in the table below:

Table 7: Test Results for Average Variance Extracted (AVE) of Vocational High School Students 53 and Telkom Vocational Schools

Indikator	Vocational High School 53	Telkom Vocational Schools
	AVE	AVE
Trust	0.540	0.559
Quality	0.527	0.522
Brand image	0.513	0.512
Decision to choose	0.687	0.544

Source: Processed by the author, 2018

Based on Table 7 all indicators of Vocational High School 53 students and Telkom Vocational Schools in each construct have a value of > 0.5 which means all indicators are valid. The decision indicator in SMK 53 gets the highest score of 0.687 according to Schiffman and Kanuk (2007) stating that the decision process as an important process is influenced by the external environment consisting of marketing mix and socio-cultural environment amounting to 0.559.

Construct Reliability Test results

The construct reliability test can be done with two measurement criteria, namely Composite reliability and cronbach alpha from the indicator block that measures the construct. Constructs are declared reliable if the composite reliability value is above 0.70 (Ghozali, 2008). The results of the reliability of two schools can be seen in Table 8 below:

Based on Table 8. The results of the composite reliability test prove the accuracy, consistency and accuracy of the instruments in measuring the constructs of

Telkom and SMK 53 students above 0.70 which means that all indicators show reliability.

Table 8: Composite Reliability Test Results of Vocational High School 53 students and Telkom Vocational Schools

Indikator	Vocational High School 53	Telkom Vocational Schools
	Composite Reliability	Composite Reliability
Trust	0.853	0.863
Quality	0.814	0.938
Brand image	0.840	0.913
Decision to choose	0.815	0.855

Source: Processed by the author, 2018

Figure 2. Respecific analysis diagram of the final model of PLS SMK 53

Figure 3. Respecific analysis diagram of the final PLS model of Telkom Vocational School

RESULT

Hypothesis testing is done to answer the research equation. To answer the hypothesis proposed in the study, bootstrapping techniques are carried out. Bootstrapping technique is a random sample data recalculation technique to obtain T-statistic and original sample values by testing path coefficients. Based on the T-statistic value obtained, it can be seen the significance level of the effect of the independent variable on the dependent variable. If the value of T-statistic is > 1.96 (T-table of significance is 5%) then the effect is significant and vice versa, below Table 9 results from path coefficient test of two schools:

Table 9: Path Test Results The Coefficient of Bootstrapping techniques of SMKN 53 students and Telkom Vocational Schools

Path	Vocational High School 53 P Values	Telkom Vocational High School P Values
X2 – X3	0.009	0.098
X1 – Y	0.010	0.250
X2 – X1	0.000	0.000
X2 – X3	0.001	0.007
X2 – Y	0.073	0.009
X3 – Y	0.000	0.646

Source: Processed by the author, 2018
 Information:
 X1 : Trust
 X2 : Quality
 X3 : Brand image
 Y : Decision to choose

From Table 9, it can be seen the result of the Path Coefficient by using Bootstrapping techniques of students from two schools. The result of the first hypothesis Trust is significant to Brand Image seen from the value of p values 0.009. This result is in accordance with the hypothesis of the researchers who said that there was an influence between the Trust and the Brand Image, therefore the hypothesis is accepted.

This result is in line with Danny's (2014) research, from the results of the research, that the Brand Image has a significant and positive influence on Trust. As well as the results of this study supported by a preliminary study (2009) showed that there is a significant positive effect between Brand Image and Trust in Batavia Air airline service customers. At SMK Telkom

the Trust is not significant to Brand Image, seen from the value of p value 0.098. This result is not in accordance with the researchers' hypothesis which stated that there is an influence between trust and brand image, so the first hypothesis in SMK Telkom is rejected. This result is in line with Niken Permata Sari (2014) with the results stating that trust does not significantly influence the brand image of the product.

The result of the second hypothesis in SMKN 53 there is a significant influence between trust and decision to choose, it can be seen from the value of p value 0.010. This result is in accordance with the hypothesis of the researchers, that there is a significant influence between trust and decision to choose, therefore the hypothesis is accepted. Maria (2015) from the results of this study has a significant effect between trust and the decision to choose on social media in Shapeharve.

At SMK Telkom for the results of the second hypothesis there is no significant effect between trust and the decision to choose with a value p value of 0.250. This result is not in accordance with the hypothesis of the researchers which stated that there is a significant influence between trust and the decision to choose, the second hypothesis is rejected. This result is in line with Inas Rafidah (2017) which stated that trust does not have a significant effect on the decision to choose on online purchases at Lazada.

The result of the third hypothesis showed that both of these schools, SMKN 53 and SMK Telkom, have a significant influence between quality and trust with the same p values, which is 0,000 at SMKN 53 and SMK Telkom. The results of this hypothesis are in accordance with the researcher's hypothesis which states that there is a significant effect between quality and trust, therefore the hypothesis is accepted. This result is supported by a previous study by Edy (2010) from the results of this study that has a significant effect between quality and trust in

customers staying at Jambuluwuk Batu Resort in Batu City and reinforced by Candra Hakim's research (2014) that quality has a significant influence on trust in Bicycle Buyers Honda Vario motorbike at PT Sumber Purnama Sakti in Gresik Regency.

Result of the fourth hypothesis SMKN 53 and SMK Telkom have a significant effect on the quality of the brand image with p values of 0.001 at SMKN 53 and 0.007 in the value of p values at the SMK Telkom. This result is in accordance with the researcher's hypothesis which states that there is a significant effect of quality on brand image, the hypothesis is accepted. This result is in line with the study of Muhamad Ridho (2017) from the results of this study that has a significant effect on brand image in prepaid sympathy customers, Malang city and also strengthened by Angelina's research (2014) stating that quality has a significant effect on brand image in Popular Bakery.

The result of the fifth hypothesis in SMKN 53 did not significantly influence the quality of the decision to choose with the value of p values 0.073. This result is not in accordance with the researcher's hypothesis which states that there is a significant influence between the qualities of the decision to choose, therefore the hypothesis is rejected. These results are in accordance with Arnoldi's research (2013) from the results of this study indicated that the quality of schools did not significantly influence the decision to choose at Al-Azhar 12 Islamic Middle School, Rawamangun.

Different from the SMKN 53, the results of the fifth hypothesis at SMK Telkom, there is a significant effect between the quality and decision to choose with the value p value 0.009. This result is in accordance with the hypothesis of the researcher stated that there is a significant influence between the quality and decision to choose, therefore the hypothesis is accepted. These results are in accordance with Bayu Sutrisna's study (2016) with the results of the study showed that quality has

a significant effect on the decision to choose at Starbucks.

The result of the sixth hypothesis in SMK 53 has a significant effect between brand image and the decision to choose with a value of p values of 0,000. This result is in accordance with the researcher's hypothesis that brand image has a significant effect on the decision to choose, therefore the hypothesis is accepted. The result of the Karina's study (2011) shows that brand image has a significant effect on the decision to choose in the Diploma III Program of the Faculty of Economics, Diponegoro University, Semarang.

Contrast with SMK Telkom, the result of the sixth hypothesis indicates that the brand image does not significantly influence the decision to choose with a value of p values of 0.646. This result is not in accordance with the hypothesis of the researchers stating that there is a significant influence between the brand image of the decision to choose, then the hypothesis is rejected. These results are consistent with Rahma Tiara Hakim's research (2013) that brand image has no significant effect on the decision to choose Sidamethrin 50 EC Brand Pesticide Products. In this study, researchers did not only influence directly, but indirectly tested the hypothesis aims to see which factors have more influence on the decisions of students in choosing vocational schools, both State Vocational and Private Vocational Schools. The following are the results of the indirect effects of two schools which can be seen in Table 10 below:

Table 10 Indirect Effects of Vocational High School Students 53 and Telkom Vocational Schools

Path	Vocational High School 53 P Values	Telkom Vocational Schools P Values
X2 – X1 – X3	0.013	0.106
X2 – X1 – Y	0.015	0.265
X2 – X1 – X3 – Y	0.054	0.716
X2 – X3 – Y	0.017	0.676

Source: Processed by the author, 2018

Information:

X1 : Trust

X2 : Quality

X3 : Brand image

Y : Decision to choose

Based on the results of Table 10, it can be explained that SMKN 53 students have a significant indirect effect between quality and trust in brand image as an intervening variable and have a p value of 0.013. These results are in accordance with the researchers' hypothesis which states that there is a significant indirect effect between quality and trust in brand image as an intervening variable, so this hypothesis is accepted. For Telkom Vocational School the indirect influence between quality and trust in brand image is not significant with p values of 0.106, therefore the researchers' hypothesis at SMK Telkom is rejected.

On indirect connection quality through trust in making a decision, get a significant effect with the value of p values 0.015. This result is in accordance with the researcher's hypothesis, therefore the hypothesis is accepted. At SMK Telkom the results of indirect influence between quality and trust in making the decision to choose the result is not significant with a value of p values 0.265. This result is not in accordance with the researcher's hypothesis, therefore the hypothesis is rejected.

The indirect influence connection of quality affects trust to the brand image continued to make decision to choose with the result is not significant for both schools, with a p value of 0.054 for SMKN 53 and p values for 0.716 for SMK Telkom.

On the relation of the influence of quality through brand image on making decision to choose has a significant influence with a value of p value 0.017 in SMKN 53. These results are consistent with the hypothesis of researchers who stated there is an indirect influence between quality through brand image on the making decision to choose, therefore the hypothesis is accepted, while the result on indirect effect of quality through brand image on the making decision to choose at SMK Telkom is not significant with a value of p values 0.676. This result is not in accordance with the researcher's hypothesis, therefore this hypothesis is rejected.

DISCUSSION

Based on the analysis result obtained, managerial implication academically is expected to be information to the education. The implications for State Vocational Schools are aimed at influencing students' decisions to be the first choice of students. In order to face competition with Private Vocational Schools, State Vocational Schools must maintain the trust in the brand image that has been well created for students, by the trust from environment that students will decide to choose a State Vocational School based on their beliefs. The quality of State Vocational Schools such as the facilities available in the learning process must be adapted to the latest technological developments so that the quality of the State Vocational School can compete with national and international Private Vocational Schools and teachers at State Vocational Schools must receive training every year so that they are competent and qualified on their fields in order to increase the confidence of students in the State Vocational School, from the quality provided by the State Vocational School to their students can make a good brand image of the its school and even become a reference State Vocational High School from the government to held training for students and teachers in the region. For Private Vocational Schools by the results obtained must maintain students' trust, so that the brand image created by Private Vocational Schools on students is not as the second choice, with a good trust created by Private Vocational Schools, it will influence the students' decision to choose at the time of admission for new students, so that Private Vocational Schools can compete with State Vocational Schools. Brand image of Private Vocational Schools can influence the decision to choose, so private Vocational High Schools must have many achievements and have majors that have high demand for working and business.

The results of managerial implications of State Vocational Schools and Private Vocational Schools to gain

school attractiveness towards parents, therefore State Vocational Schools must have qualities that can be seen by parents, such as the availability of facilities that support students in learning so that they can influence the trust of parents to send their children whether to State Vocational School or Private Vocational School. Quality can create a good brand image for parents, so that State Vocational Schools and Private Vocational Schools must have a characteristic in order to become a reference school for other schools, by maintaining the quality of the State Vocational School will influence of the decision to choose of parents. Private Vocational Schools must make a good brand image by providing competent teachers in their fields, clean school environment, accredited schools and complete facilities that influence parents' decisions in sending their children to private vocational schools.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of data analysis there are differences factors that influence the decision to choose on the learners and parents at SMKN 53 and SMK Telkom, therefore obtained some conclusions:

Characteristics of students in the two schools are dominated by men, 100% in SMKN 53 and 69% in SMK Telkom, while by age there are similarities on students of SMKN 53 and SMK Telkom which is at the age of 16 years with 68% of SMK 53 and 69% of SMK Telkom. Based on the majors, students in SMKN 53 majoring in Electricity get a percentage of 26% while 26% for SMK Telkom for network majors.

Based on the hypothesis test result directly shows that on students in SMKN 53 there is an insignificant influence between the quality and the decision to choose with the value of T statistics is 1.798 while on students of SMK Telkom there are insignificant influences on: Trust on brand image with T value statistics 1,660. Trust on decision of choosing with value T statistics 1,151. Brand Image on decision of choosing with value T statistics 0.460.

The results of indirect hypothesis testing in SMKN 53 students have three influential and significant: Quality and Trust have indirectly effect on brand image. Quality and trust have an indirect effect on the decision to choose. Quality and brand image has an indirect effect on the decision to choose, while on students of SMK Telkom Vocational, by indirect relation, there is not significant for all tested variables.

SUGGESTION

Expanding the scope of research, which is not only limited to vocational schools but also to Senior High School (SMA) or Islamic Senior High School (MA). This is to get more comprehensive results related to the factors that influence brand image on the decision to choose.

For Private Vocational Schools it is important for maintaining the trust of students and parents towards brand image in order to be able to compete with State Vocational Schools, because trust can directly influence the decision of choosing students and parents.

For State Vocational Schools it is important for maintaining quality, both in facilities and infrastructure and educators because the quality of schools affects students and parents in choosing vocational schools.

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How to cite this article: Setiyadi R, Najib M, Sarma DM. Millennial generation decisions in choosing vocational schools. *International Journal of Research and Review*. 2019; 6(4):71-81.
